

RESIDUAL COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH ASSESSMENT OF IMPACTED LAMINATES BASED ON C-SCAN DATA

Y. Yang^{1*}, X. Sun², S. Li¹

¹ Faculty of Engineering, University of Nottingham, Nottingham NG7 2RD, UK

² Aircraft Strength Research Institute, Xi'an 710065, China

* Corresponding author (emxyy2@nottingham.ac.uk)

Keywords: *impact, delamination, compression, CAI, C-scan*

1 Abstract

A method of CAI prediction based on C-scan data is presented, in which impact-delaminated area is considered as a soft inclusion in the laminate. A prediction of CAI is presented through calculating the strength of the impacted laminate under compression as a consequence of stress concentration rather than delamination propagation, while the determination of delaminations in the impact damage zone is based on the C-scan data obtained experimentally. The technique helps to avoid complicated modelling and challenging numerical convergence difficulties.

2 Introduction

It is well-known that laminated composites are susceptible to foreign object impact, usually classified as low-velocity impact, which could result in as much as 60% strength loss without obvious surface damage [1]. A significant number of compression after impact (CAI) tests have been conducted to determine the allowable design values. It is a common practice that impacted structures with the extent of damage below a threshold can be properly repaired as a compromise between safety and economy. A practical method of assessing the CAI strength is instrumental to assist the design and maintenance of such structures.

The common view about damage mechanism of CAI is that the delaminated area buckles when the impacted laminate is subjected to in-plane compression, and sublaminates in this area have a tendency of relative movements which may result in rising stress levels around delamination crack tips. With the increasing compressive load, the delamination propagation can be triggered when the energy release rate (ERR) at the crack tip exceeds its threshold. The whole laminate could collapse because of unstable delamination propagation. [2-4].

To reflect the above mechanism, a conventional approach employed by many researchers is to simulate buckling and delamination propagation using FEM to predict the process as described above [2-8]. This approach however is only applicable for cases where there are few delaminations, such as artificially pre-inserted delaminations. It is impractical and even impossible to simulate all possible delaminations induced by impact as they could be present at all interlaminar interfaces of the laminate. Simulations of such problems using FEM often encounter significant convergence difficulties resulting from geometrical nonlinearity, structural instability and contact conditions.

There is another view on the failure of CAI. It can be considered as stress concentration in impact damaged laminate rather than unstable delamination propagation. This resembles the case of compression of a plate with an open-hole where stress concentration arises around the edge of the open-hole. The difference between CAI and open-hole case is that impact damaged area can still sustain some stresses as a softened inclusion as opposed to an open-hole [9, 10].

To simulate the mechanism of a softened inclusion, a relatively simple method to predict the CAI is presented in this paper. A reduced stiffness is assigned to the impact damaged area and the CAI failure is predicted as a consequence of in-plane compression failure due to stress concentration. This method avoids the high demands on the mesh generation and simulation of the complicated interlaminar interactions for the model and challenging numerical convergence difficulties. The key part of this approach is a proper way of determining the stiffness degradation of the impact damaged area, a generally applicable form of which is unfortunately still unavailable yet. In the present paper, the stiffness degradation rule as introduced in

[10] is adopted to facilitate the analysis while the emphasis of the present paper will be placed on the evaluation of the size of the impact damaged area and its implementation in an analysis of this kind.

3 Methodology

The CAI prediction method presented in this paper is inspired by the mechanism that the ultimate CAI strength is characterised as a sequence of failures at sublaminar level due to in-plane stress concentration. Such a process is relatively simple to model and computationally efficient. The novelty of this paper is the use of data obtained from nonconductive inspection (ultrasonic C-scan) for the description of the delamination distribution within the impact damaged laminate. The C-scan detected delamination data is imported into the model to facilitate the prediction of CAI failure.

3.1 Delamination data from C-scan

In this paper, specimens of 150mm × 100mm were used. The dimensions are as recommended in the ASTM test standard [11]. The layup sequence is [45/0/-45/90]_{3S} with nominal thickness 4.56mm. These specimens were divided into 5 groups according to the impact energy, 15J, 30J, 40J, 50J and 60J, respectively. It is well-known that delaminations distribute along the thickness direction with a “pine” shape. If one point of delamination at an interlaminar interface shares the same in-plane coordinates with another delamination closer to the C-scan sensor, it will be “shaded” and its existence cannot be detected directly, resulting a blind zone as illustrated in Fig. 1(a). In order to detect delaminations as completely as possible, the specimens were scanned on both sides (Fig. 1(a) and (b)). Even so, the delaminations within the core may still not be detected because of the “shadow” projected from delaminations closer to the surfaces (Fig. 1(c)). However, according to the experience from impact simulation and de-ply experiments [12], it can be reasonably assumed that in the “shaded” area is fully delaminated (Fig. 1(d)).

Based on the assumption and argument above, delamination configurations can be depicted, for example, at the section of specimen cut along the longitudinal central line in Fig. 1(d). It can be seen that the delamination areas at different interlaminar interfaces can be different. It is therefore necessary to use a degradation coefficient for each delaminated

lamina rather than a uniform one for all laminae in the delaminated area.

3.2 Delamination distribution in FEM model

In this paper, CAI is predicted by FE model in which shell elements are employed. Since simulation of delamination propagation is avoided in this method, only one shell element is involved in thickness direction representing the whole laminate. Although the delamination distribution is known through the methodology described in 3.1, a few steps are required in order to simulate the effect of damage due to these delaminations.

When the specimen was scanned, a delaminated spot was recorded in pixels with its depth in the z-direction also registered. The pixels representing delaminations at the same depth in the z-direction form the first part of the delamination on, for example, k^{th} interlaminar interface (Fig. 2(a)). The other part of the delamination on the same interlaminar interface is obtained as follows. If first part of delamination as described above is obtained from scanning on the impact side (refer to Fig. 1(a)), the delaminations from 1st to $(k-1)^{\text{th}}$ interfaces are superimposed to form the second part of the delamination on the k^{th} interface. Otherwise if it is obtained by scanning on the back side (Fig. 1(b)), the second part forms by superimpose the delaminations from the $(k+1)^{\text{th}}$ to the last interlaminar interfaces. The delamination on the k^{th} interface is obtained as the sum of the two parts as described above (Fig. 2(b)). However, the shape of delamination in Fig. 2(b) is usually not regular enough to be described by an analytical expression to allow straightforward buckling analysis for the evaluation of the degradation coefficient as will be addressed later. In this paper, the shape of delamination in each interlaminar surface is further approximated as an ellipse (Fig. 2(b)), which circumscribes the irregular delamination area as obtained previously with its long axis coincident with the fibre direction of the next lamina away from the impact side of the laminate in line with the tendency as observed in experiments. Mapping this elliptical delamination onto the FE mesh, it will be convenient for subsequent modelling that any partially delaminated element is considered as fully delaminated (Fig. 2(c)) and the stiffness degradation will be applied correspondingly for delaminated laminae.

Fig. 1 Schematic of delamination distribution at specimen's section plane (material system: T700/BA9918, ply sequence: $[45/0/-45/90]_{3S}$, impact energy: 60J)

(a) Scanned delamination on k^{th} interface (1st part)

(b) Superimposed with the 2nd part and approximated as an ellipse

(c) Delamination on the k^{th} interface in the FE model

Fig. 2 Illustrative schematic of introducing scanned delamination into FEA model

The generalised stress-strain relationship for a shell element with delamination damage can be expressed as

$$\begin{cases} N = \sum_{k=1}^n d_k Q_k \left[(z_k - z_{k-1}) \varepsilon^0 + \frac{1}{2} (z_k^2 - z_{k-1}^2) \kappa \right] \\ M = \sum_{k=1}^n d_k Q_k \left[\frac{1}{2} (z_k^2 - z_{k-1}^2) \varepsilon^0 + \frac{1}{3} (z_k^3 - z_{k-1}^3) \kappa \right] \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where d_k is the degradation coefficient of k^{th} lamina; N , M , the sectional membrane forces and moments respectively; Q_k , the lamina stiffness matrix of the k^{th} unidirectional ply in the global laminate

coordinate system; z_k , the thickness direction coordinate of the k^{th} interlaminar interface; ε^0 the membrane strains and K the curvatures.

3.3 Definition the degradation coefficient

The degradation coefficient d_k is defined as

$$d_k = \frac{N_k/t_k}{\sigma^0} \quad (2)$$

where N_k is the buckling load of the k^{th} delaminated layer; t_k the thickness of the k^{th} delaminated layer; σ^0 the compression strength of undamaged laminate.

3.4 Definition of N_k

N_k is the buckling load of the k^{th} sublaminate which is obtained through the following procedure. Assume that none of the delaminated lamina has buckled (Fig.3 (a)) at beginning.

Step 1

Carry out the buckling analysis for sublaminate Sub_1^{left} (it consists of only the 1st layer from the surface on the left) and defined the buckling load as N_1^{left} . Repeat the same process for sublaminate Sub_1^{right} (it consists of all layers from 2nd to n^{th}) and obtain the buckling load as N_1^{right} (Fig.3 (b)). The buckling analyses are based on the assumption that the sublaminates on both sides of the delamination of a shape identical to the delamination, i.e. ellipse, with their edges fully clamped. The principles of the analyses will be presented later.

Step 2

Considering the procedure as presented in Step 1 as the analyses for delamination 1, repeat the same procedure as in Step 1 for the each of the subsequent delaminations. A series of buckling loads (N_1^{left} , N_1^{right} , ..., N_k^{left} , N_k^{right} , ..., N_n^{left} , N_n^{right}) are obtained. Find the minimum of them and identify the sublaminate it is associated with. This sublaminate buckles as the load to the laminate increases to this level (Fig.3 (c)).

Step 3

Treat the remaining unbuckled sublaminates (Fig.3 (d)) in the same way as the laminate in Step 1 and 2, another buckling load can be obtained with another sublaminate buckled. Eventually every sublaminate will be associated with a buckling load. The buckling load obtained for the sublaminate will be used to evaluate the stiffness degradation coefficient as introduced in (2) for this sublaminate.

Fig. 3 Illustrative schematic on of N definition (side view of the delaminated plate)

3.5 Calculation of N_k

The algorithm in this paper is adopted from [13]. In order to calculate the buckling load of elliptical delaminated sublaminates whose long axis lies at an angle of θ from global X axis, the deflection function is assumed in its local (material) coordinates x and y as

$$w(x, y) = \left(1 - \left(\frac{x}{a}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{y}{b}\right)^2\right)^2 (C_1 + C_2x + C_3y + C_4x^2 + C_5xy + C_6y^2) \quad (3)$$

where a , b are the long and short half axes respectively. The total potential energy of the delaminated sublaminates is

$$\Pi_p = \frac{1}{2} \int_{-a}^a \int_{-b\sqrt{1-(x/a)^2}}^{b\sqrt{1-(x/a)^2}} \left(\begin{matrix} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} \\ \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2} \\ 2 \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x \partial y} \end{matrix} \right)^T [D] \left(\begin{matrix} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} \\ \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2} \\ 2 \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x \partial y} \end{matrix} \right) - \left(\begin{matrix} \frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \\ \frac{\partial w}{\partial y} \end{matrix} \right)^T \begin{bmatrix} N_1 & N_{12} \\ N_{12} & N_2 \end{bmatrix} \left(\begin{matrix} \frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \\ \frac{\partial w}{\partial y} \end{matrix} \right) dydx \quad (4)$$

where D is the bending stiffness matrix of the sublaminates according to the classical laminate theory; N_1 , N_2 , N_{12} , the membrane forces in the sublaminates in its local coordinate system. Since membrane strains in the delaminated sublaminates in its material coordinates can be expressed as

$$\begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_1 \\ \varepsilon_2 \\ \gamma_{12} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & a_{16} \\ a_{12} & a_{22} & a_{26} \\ a_{16} & a_{26} & a_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} N_X \\ N_Y \\ N_{XY} \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

where a_{ij} are the compliance of the delaminated sublaminates in its material coordinates, under uniaxial compression,

$$N_Y = N_{XY} = 0 \quad (6)$$

membrane strains in the delaminated sublaminates in its material coordinates can be given as

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_1 \\ \varepsilon_2 \\ \gamma_{12} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \rho_1 \\ \rho_2 \\ \rho_{12} \end{Bmatrix} N_X \quad (7)$$

where

$$\begin{cases} \rho_1 = a_{11} \cos^2 \theta + a_{12} \sin^2 \theta - a_{16} \sin \theta \cos \theta \\ \rho_2 = a_{12} \cos^2 \theta + a_{22} \sin^2 \theta - a_{26} \sin \theta \cos \theta \\ \rho_{12} = a_{16} \cos^2 \theta + a_{26} \sin^2 \theta - a_{66} \sin \theta \cos \theta \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

Thus

$$\begin{Bmatrix} N_1 \\ N_2 \\ N_{12} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} & A_{16} \\ A_{12} & A_{22} & A_{26} \\ A_{16} & A_{26} & A_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_1 \\ \varepsilon_2 \\ \gamma_{12} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} n_1 \\ n_2 \\ n_{12} \end{Bmatrix} N_X \quad (9)$$

where

$$\begin{cases} n_1 = A_{11}\rho_1 + A_{12}\rho_2 + A_{16}\rho_{12} \\ n_2 = A_{12}\rho_1 + A_{22}\rho_2 + A_{26}\rho_{12} \\ n_{12} = A_{16}\rho_1 + A_{26}\rho_2 + A_{66}\rho_{12} \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

Substituting Eq. (9) into Eq. (4), the variational principle leads to an eigenvalue problem

$$([K] - N_X[K_g])\{C\} = 0 \quad (11)$$

where $[K]$ and $[K_g]$ are the stiffness and geometric stiffness matrices, respectively. $\{C\}$ is a vector containing constants in Eq. (3) to be determined. The lowest eigenvalue for N_X gives the critical load for the sublaminates under consideration.

3.6 Evaluation of CAI

When the FEA model of the laminate with degraded stiffness in the delaminated area is created, the CAI strength can be predicted as the highest compressive load applied to the laminate. In this paper, Hashin's criterion [14] is employed for the in-plane failure. Some of the results obtained are presented in Fig. 4 and 5, which seem to provide a reasonable approximation to the test data. As a result, it is expected that the present approach provides a pragmatic solution to CAI strength prediction and is capable of obtaining relatively accurate evaluations of the CAI strength in an efficient way. As an illustration, an example of such a problem has been analysed. The mesh involves about 1600 nodes and yet it only took about 5 minutes to run on a PC.

Fig. 4 Comparison of calculation and test result (T700/BA9918, [45/0/-45/90]_{3S})

Fig. 5 Comparison of calculation and test result (T700/QY9611, [45/0/-45/90]_{5S})

4 Conclusions

In this paper, a relatively simple method of CAI strength prediction is presented, in which the delaminated area due to impact is considered as a softened material included in the laminate. Such assumption leads to the benefit of relatively simple model construction, and it also helps to avoid significant convergence difficulties due to geometrical nonlinearity, structural instability and contact conditions.

In addition, the delaminations are obtained from C-scan data over the impacted area, that are introduced into the model directly. This can be really useful for airplane in-field inspections. Traditionally, the main approach of in-field inspection is by “walk around” to examine dent depth on the airplane’s outer surface caused by external object impact [15]. It is risky to judge the loading capability of the structure mainly by the surface appearance, because the impact damage associated with relatively insignificant surface dents may aggravate with time while material properties decay locally under the combined effects of fatigue and aging. Nowadays, a

portable C-scan device is readily available. A residual-strength-predicting system can be developed working together with this portable C-scan device in field to improve the maintenance efficiency and flight safety. In such a system, importing real damage data into predicting model is one of the critical steps.

The present method is limited to CAI strength prediction of laminated panels rather than the the actual failure mechanism. Nevertheless, this method complies with the test standard [11] which has been widely accepted to be used to determine the allowable values, it should have its own value practically.

References

- [1] Pavel Sztefek, Robin Olsson. “Nonlinear compressive stiffness in impacted composite laminates determined by an inverse method”. *Composites: Part A*, Vol. 40, No. 3, pp 260-272, 2009.
- [2] Sun Xiannian, Chen Haoran, Su Changjian, Liu Xiangbin. “Delamination Growth in Composite Laminates”. *Acta Mechanica Sinica*, Vol. 32, No. 2, pp 223-232, 2000.
- [3] Hiroshi Suemasu, Wataru Sasaki. “A Numerical Study on Compressive Behavior of Composite Plates with Multiple Circular Delaminations Considering Delamination Propagation”. *Composite Science and Technology*, Vol. 68, No. 12, pp 2562-2567, 2008.
- [4] Andrew T. Rhead, Richard Butler. “Compressive Static Strength Model for Impact Damaged Laminates”. *Composite Science and Technology*, Vol. 69, No. 14, pp 2301-2307, 2009.
- [5] K.-F. Nilsson, J. C. Thesken, P. Sindelar. “A theoretical and experimental investigation of buckling induced delamination growth”. *Journal of Mechanics and Physics solids*, Vol. 41, No. 4, pp 749-782, 1993.
- [6] L. Gunnar Melin, Joakim Schon. “Buckling behavior and delamination growth in impacted composite specimens under fatigue Load: an experimental study”. *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 61, No. 13, pp 1841-1852, 2001.
- [7] Hwang S-F, Liu G-H. “Buckling behavior of composite laminates with multiple delaminations under uniaxial compression”. *Composites Structures*, Vol. 53, No. 2, pp 235-243, 2001.
- [8] K.-F. Nilsson, L. E. Asp, J. E. Alpmann, L. Nystedt. “Delamination buckling and growth for

delaminations at different depths in a slender composite panel”. *Internal Journal of Solids and Structures*, Vol. 38, No. 17, pp 3039-3071, 2001.

- [9] Chen Puhui, Shen Zhen, Wang Junyang, “A new method for compression after impact strength prediction of composite laminates”. *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol. 36, No. 5, pp 589-610, 2002.
- [10] Tang X, Shen Z, Chen P, Gadke M. “Methodology for residual strength of damaged laminated composites”. Proceedings of the 38th AIAA/ASME/AHS/ASC structure, structural dynamics and material conference, CP-AIAA-97-1220, 1997.
- [11] American Society for Testing and Materials. ASTM D 7137/D 7137M-07: Standard Test Method for Compressive Residual Strength Properties of Damaged Polymer Matrix Composite Plates. United States: ASTM, 2007.
- [12] Tang Xiaodong, Shen Zhen, Liu Junshi. “The Deply technic for damage detection of composite laminate”. *Acta Materiae Compositae Sinica*, Vol. 3, No. 3, pp 70-74, 1986.
- [13] Tang Xiaodong, Liu Feng. “Theory manual of CDTAC 1.0”. *ASRI technical report*, 623S-9801-19, 1998.
- [14] Z Hashin, “Failure criteria for unidirectional fiber composite”. *Journal of applied mechanics*, Vol. 47, No. 2, pp 329-334, 1980.
- [15] Federal Aviation Administration. “Advisory Circular 20-107B: Composite Aircraft Structure”. United States: U. S. Department of Transportation, 2009.